

Authors	Article Title	Date
Abecasis, D; Afonso, P; O'Dor, RK; Erzini, K	Small MPAs do not protect cuttlefish (<i>Sepia officinalis</i>)	2013
Cunha, AH; Erzini, K; Serrao, EA; Gonçalves, E; Borges, R; Henriques, M; Henriques, V; Guerra, M; Duarte, C; Marbá, N; Fonseca, M	Biomares, a LIFE project to restore and manage the biodiversity of Prof. Luiz Saldanha Marine Park	2014
Kraft, S; Winkler, AC; Abecasis, D	Small coastal marine protected areas offer recurring, seasonal protection to the common stingray (<i>Dasvatis pastinaca</i>)	2023
Kraft, S; Winkler, AC; Abecasis, D	Seasonal movement dynamics of the commercially important thornback ray (<i>Raja clavata</i>) in a coastal marine protected area	2024
Henriques, V; Guerra, MT; Mendes, B; Gaudêncio, MJ; Fonseca, P	Benthic habitat mapping in a Portuguese Marine Protected Area using EUNIS: An integrated approach	2015
da Silva, CP; Mendes, RN; Moutinho, G; Mota, V; Fonseca, C	Beach carrying capacity and protected areas: management issues in Arrabida Natural Park, Portugal	2016
Borges, R; Vaz, J; Serrao, EA; Gonçalves, EJ	Short-term Temporal Fluctuation of Very-nearshore Larval Fish Assemblages at the Arrabida Marine Park (Portugal)	2009
Lopes, R; Videira, N	A Collaborative Approach for Scoping Ecosystem Services with Stakeholders: The Case of Arrabida Natural Park	2016
Martínez-Ramírez, L; Priester, CR; Sousa, I; Erzini, K; Abecasis, D	Reserve effect of a small North-East Atlantic marine protected area (Arrabida, Portugal) on soft-sediment fish species	2021
Costa, BHE; Erzini, K; Caselle, JE; Folhas, H; Gonçalves, EJ	'Reserve effect' within a temperate marine protected area in the north-eastern Atlantic (Arrabida Marine Park, Portugal)	2013
Batista, MI; Baeta, F; Costa, MJ; Cabral, HN	MPA as management tools for small-scale fisheries: The case study of Arrabida Marine Protected Area (Portugal)	2011
Gomes, I; Peteiro, LG; Albuquerque, R; Nolasco, R; Dubert, J; Swearer, SE; Oueiroga, H	Wandering mussels: using natural tags to identify connectivity patterns among Marine Protected Areas	2016
Kraft, S; Winkler, AC; Abecasis, D	Horizontal and vertical movements of the critically endangered <i>Rostroraja alba</i> in a coastal marine protected area	2024
Cunha, AH; Assis, J; Serrao, EA	Estimation of available seagrass meadow area in Portugal for transplanting purposes.	2009
Batista, MI; Henriques, S; Pais, MP; Cabral, HN	A framework for the assessment of MPA effectiveness based on life history of fishes	2015
Lopes, R; Videira, N	Bringing stakeholders together to articulate multiple value dimensions of ecosystem services	2018

Stratoudakis, Y; Farrall, H; Vasconcelos, L	Collaborative lessons towards marine sustainability: a long-term collective engagement	2019
Rebêlo, L; Ferraz, M; Brito, P; Terrinha, P	Quantification of sediments accumulated in the NW sector of Tria Peninsula (Portugal) between 1928 and 1995	2012
Beldade, R; Erzini, K; Gonçalves, EJ	Composition and temporal dynamics of a temperate rocky cryptobenthic fish assemblage	2006
Oliveira, G; Nunes, A; Clemente, A; Correia, O	Effect of substrate treatments on survival and growth of Mediterranean shrubs in a revegetated quarry: An eight-year study	2011
Henriques, S; Pais, MP; Costa, MJ; Cabral, HN	Seasonal variability of rocky reef fish assemblages: Detecting functional and structural changes due to fishing effects	2013
Priester, CR; Martínez-Ramírez, L; Erzini, K; Abecasis, D	The impact of trammel nets as an MPA soft bottom monitoring method	2021
Solomon, FN; Rodrigues, D; Gonçalves, EJ; Serrao, EA; Borges, R	Larval development and allometric growth of the black-faced blenny <i>Tripterygion delaisi</i>	2017
Henriques, M; Gonçalves, EJ; Almada, VC	Rapid shifts in a marine fish assemblage follow fluctuations in winter sea conditions	2007
Lopes, R; Videira, N	How to articulate the multiple value dimensions of ecosystem services? Insights from implementing the PARTICULATES framework in a coastal social-ecological system in Portugal	2019
Van Beveren, E; Klein, M; Serrao, EA; Gonçalves, EJ; Borges, R	Early life history of larvae and early juvenile Atlantic horse mackerel <i>Trachurus trachurus</i> off the Portuguese west coast	2016
Silva, CSE; Novais, SC; Lemos, MFL; Mendes, S; Oliveira, AP; Gonçalves, EJ; Faria, AM	Effects of ocean acidification on the swimming ability, development and biochemical responses of sand smelt larvae	2016
Costa, BHE; Gonçalves, L; Gonçalves, EJ	Vessels' site fidelity and spatio-temporal distribution of artisanal fisheries before the implementation of a temperate multiple-use marine protected area	2013
Batista, MI; Costa, BHE; Gonçalves, L; Henriques, M; Erzini, K; Caselle, JE; Gonçalves, EJ; Cabral, HN	Assessment of catches, landings and fishing effort as useful tools for MPA management	2015